

TYPICAL DATA MODELS ARE INADEQUATE FOR HYPERTEMPORAL IMAGERY

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ABSTRACT

We highlight challenges associated with using conventional pattern recognition methods to test imagery from a persistent longwave infrared remote sensing experiment, where material surface emissivity and temperature among other factors dominate the apparent radiance observed at the sensor. We also propose a superior data model for the task.

Index Terms— Persistent imaging, longwave infrared

1. INTRODUCTION

Hypertemporal Imaging is defined as a persistent collection of multispectral or hyperspectral imagery over time. There are many challenges associated with such a dataset, to include embedded computing for real time tasks and autonomous pattern recognition for real time or forensic tasks. Ref [1] highlights some of these challenges associated with autonomous pattern recognition using such a dataset, especially in the longwave infrared (LWIR), where surface emissivity and temperature among other factors dominate the apparent radiance observed at the sensor. A multitude of adaptive detection and recognition algorithms have appeared in the literature or have found their way into software packages and end-user systems, see [2]. A common base among these approaches is that they all assume data to be independent of the time collected, or of some other factor(s) that depends on the time of the day (e.g., temperature). We start to argue in this paper that target detectors based on linear data models based on fixed parameters and/or covariates are inadequate for LWIR hyperspectral data.

2. HYPERTEMPORAL DATASET

Fig 1 illustrates the target site (top), a sample from hypertemporal mean spectra (middle) representing a given material (aluminum flat plate shown in white) in the target scene, and band average images (bottom) representing the scene in radiance at within a diurnal cycle. The target site features three metal targets (surrogates of a military tank) painted with a specific paint and posed at three aspect angles

Fig. 1. Target site and variability of its data within a diurnal cycle.

(0, 90, and 135 degrees, counterclockwise relative to the sensor's line of sight). These targets are denoted by T0, T90, and T135. The scene is dominated by a natural clutter

background (trees, soil) and other manmade objects (black canvas, a metal and concrete hut, and an aluminum flat plate that can reflect the sky radiance back to the sensor). The data were collected using the Telops LWIR HyperCam (7.5μ to 8.5μ) from a tower standing 126 m with respect to the target placement site, which is located at a slant range of 570 m out from the tower base used to house the sensor. Fig 1 (middle) depicts the variability of the spectral mean of the sky downwelling radiance in flicks, which is reflected from the white plate; the tanks and other objects in the scene also reflect some of that radiance in addition to self-emission.

Note that the most basic parameter of the underlying probability distribution function (PDF) controlling this reflected thermal energy phenomenon from an aluminum plate in the scene changes as a function of time. This change is due to overcast (see in Fig. 1 (middle) the dramatic spectral change centered on the 5:00 am time period) and high solar load conditions (see the dramatic spectral change between 10:00 am and 04:00 pm relative to other time periods) within a 24h time period. Data cubes were collected at a rate of 1 over 5 minutes. The implication is severe about this parameter change, to include the inadequateness of idealized assumptions inherent in most pattern recognition methods in the literature, e.g., multivariate samples are controlled by a fixed PDF, hence, by a fixed set of parameters. Finally, Fig. 1 (bottom) illustrates the average band images of the same target site during a diurnal cycle on 22 July 2012, where a selected number of those images are depicted. The thermal variability shown in Fig. 1 (bottom) for each object in the scene suggests that assuming a fixed probability density function to model LWIR hyperspectral data is inadequate. Therefore, the results produced by any theoretical method based on this assumption intended to perform anomaly detection, target detection, band reduction, material un-mixing, etc, should be ignored, as they are being applied in an ad hoc fashion. This assumption is made for the majority of existing methods.

3. LONGITUDINAL DATA MODELS

A better solution might be achieved by modeling remote sensing data as longitudinal. The defining characteristic of a longitudinal study is that individual entities are measured repeatedly through time. Longitudinal studies are in contrast to cross-sectional studies, in which a single outcome is measured for each individual entity. Although not widely recognized in the scientific community, the most interesting problems of predicting entity patterns are longitudinal in nature, as the procedure starts by obtaining data of the same object(s) of interest under some condition(s) and later seeking mathematical solutions to predict patterns of the same object(s) in future data. Longitudinal analysis' interest lies in studying the association between the covariates and

the response variable. To this end, a linear model is often employed:

$$Y(t) = \beta_0 + X(t)^T \mathbf{b} + \varepsilon(t) \quad (1)$$

for covariates and response variable collected at time t. See for example [3]. Despite of its success in many applications (medical, economics), model (1) does not allow the association to vary over time, even though the covariates and the response variable change over time and environment, Ref [4] proposes the following varying coefficient model

$$Y(t) = \beta_0(t) + X(t)^T \beta(t) + \varepsilon(t), \quad (2)$$

where the functional coefficients are assumed to be smooth. The coefficients in model (2) can be estimated by the kernel, polynomial and smoothing spline methods [4]. One important issue with longitudinal data analysis is how to incorporate the within subject correlation structure into the estimation procedure, which can improve the estimator during estimation. For parametric setting, this issue has been thoroughly investigated, and the methodology has been well established; see [3], which views the semivarying coefficient models as an extension of varying coefficient models. We therefore consider the semivarying coefficient models

$$y(t) = Z_1^T(t) \mathbf{a}_1(t) + Z_2^T \mathbf{a}_2 + \varepsilon(t), \quad (3)$$

where $y(t)$ in our case labels the specific material type (e.g., vehicle paint, tree, soil), $Z_i(t)$, $i = 1, 2$, is p_i dimensional covariate, $p_1 + p_2 = p$, and the expectation of the error $E\varepsilon(t) = 0$ with an unknown variance of the error $\text{var} \varepsilon(t) = \sigma^2(t)$. Modeling the covariance matrix is intrinsically challenging due to potentially sparse and irregular observed time points for each material in consideration. To take this structure into account [5] proposed the following semiparametric model. The variance function $\sigma^2(\cdot)$ are modeled nonparametrically and the correlation function parametrically: For any t and s , the correlation between $\varepsilon(t)$ and $\varepsilon(s)$ is $\rho(s, t, \theta)$. The function form of $\rho(s, t, \theta)$ is known, but θ is unknown to be estimated. In this way, the variance function $\sigma^2(t)$ is estimable nonparametrically as long as the collection of time points for all target material types are dense in a time interval of interest. On the other hand, sparse individual observations (for those materials with at least two observations) can be aggregated to estimate the parameters in the correlation function. The idea is indeed powerful and takes longitudinal data structure at heart. Suppose that a sample from (3) consists of n material types. For each i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, for the i th material, we have observation $(Z_{i1}^T(t_{ij}), Z_2(t_{ij}), y_i(t_{ij}))$ at time point $t_{ij}, j = 1, \dots, J_i$. Let $\varepsilon_i(t_{ij})$ be the $\varepsilon(t)$

corresponding to $(Z_1^T(t_{ij}), Z_2(t_{ij}), y_i(t_{ij}))$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i = (\varepsilon_i(t_{i1}), \dots, \varepsilon_i(t_{iJ}))^T$. Denote the covariance matrix of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i$ by Σ_i . Of interest is estimating model parameters $\mathbf{a}_1(\cdot), \mathbf{a}_2, \sigma^2(\cdot)$, and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, which is covered in detail in [5].

4. EXPERIMENT WITH HYPERTEMPORAL DATA

As a proof of principle experiment, using a 7×7 window, the same set of hyperspectral samples representing a full diurnal cycle of the target paint (paint of T0, T90, and T135) were used to train four methods: Support vector data description (SVDD) [6], model shown in (1), model in (2), and model in (3); where in this case SVDD represents a standard approach of target detection, which does not take into account the correlation among data points over time. Test results are quantified using data over a period of three consecutive days-daytime and nighttime, where the first diurnal cycle corresponds to the period wherein the training samples were taken from, while samples of the remainder two cycles were not seen by the methods before the test; see Fig. 2. The test is conducted by applying each method, and corresponding estimated parameters from training, to all possible overlapping 7×7 block of data within each data cube. Fig. 2 illustrates the probability of correct target paint detection (PD) as a function of time, i.e., the period of 72 h (three diurnal cycles), starting on 6 March 2010 at 00:00 AM (midnight) and ending on 8 March 2010 at 11:55 PM, for a fixed false alarm probability (PFA = 0.05). Starting with the SVDD performance plot (blue) in Fig. 2, three conspicuous humps are clearly featured in the correct PD plots during daytime. Although the peaks of these humps do not even reach the value of PD = 0.4, those results validate the effect of sun loading at a faster rate during daytime on all manmade objects (including the target paint) in the scene as a cyclical phenomenon to be expected during daytime. Since SVDD, or any other procedure that does not take into account the correlation between data points across time during training, the correct detection during daytime was easier to achieve (although at a relatively lower level) than during nighttime when the temperature of all objects in the scene significantly decreased after sunset, especially for manmade objects. In contrast, models (1), (2), and (3), which take into account the correlation of the samples across time during training and differ only among themselves in the approach to estimate training parameters, can correctly detect the paint of the three tanks at a higher level than SVDD can, independently of time within a diurnal cycle. Regarding the significantly better performance of model (3) across time relative to the other two models, we can only offer at this early stage of research the justification that the detector using model (3) employs two steps in order to account for two competing facts. On one hand, the estimation of σ^2 and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ depends on the estimation of $\mathbf{a}_1(\cdot)$

and \mathbf{a}_2 . On the other hand, the estimation of $\mathbf{a}_1(\cdot)$ and \mathbf{a}_2 can be improved by using the estimate of σ^2 and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Therefore, the initial estimators of $\mathbf{a}_1(\cdot)$ and \mathbf{a}_2 are constructed by ignoring the within subject correlation. With these estimators, we can estimate σ^2 and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Finally, we can estimate $\mathbf{a}_1(\cdot)$ and \mathbf{a}_2 more efficiently by using the estimators of σ^2 and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. We applied the profile least squares estimation suggested by [5], using a kernel estimator as a natural estimator of σ^2 (as suggested in [5]), and estimated $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ by minimizing a quasi-likelihood function suggested in [5] with respect to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

Fig. 2. Performance across time within three diurnal cycles; detectors were trained using data from the first diurnal cycle. Four detectors were trained using samples from the first 24 hours (00:00 to 24:00) and tested entire imagery from three diurnal cycles. Detectors using models (1), (2), and (3) take into account the correlation of the samples across time.

5. FUTURE WORK

Results discussed in this paper suggest that detectors based on the estimation of fixed parameters are inadequate to effectively perform their tasks using hypertemporal LWIR imagery. The quasi-likelihood estimator using model (3) is a good estimator when the correlation structure is correctly specified. However, when correlation structure is misspecified, this estimator may incur a larger bias. We plan on proposing a more robust estimator which is based on minimizing the generalized variance of \mathbf{a}_2 .

6. REFERENCES

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